

A Novel Flavone Glycoside from the Seeds of *Crotalaria laburnifolia* Linn.

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Crotalaria laburnifolia Linn.¹ (N.O. Leguminosae) is commonly known as 'Muna' and occurs in Western Peninsula, Northern Andhra, Mysore, Travancore, Sri Lanka, Malaya and Phillipines. The medicinal importance of the plant is reported to be useful as gargle to cure sore throat and inflammation of the mouth².

C. laburnifolia Linn. was supplied by M/s. United Chemicals and Allied Products, Calcutta and authenticated by the Department of Botany, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar³.

Air-dried, powdered and defatted seeds of *Crotalaria laburnifolia* Linn. was extracted with hot 95% EtOH and concentrated under reduced pressure to a brown viscous mass, which was separated into water-soluble and -insoluble parts. The water-soluble part was concentrated and successively extracted with benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol. The chloroform-soluble fraction on tlc examination, showed two spots (chromatographed over a column of Si-gel with various proportions of chloroform : methanol : water). The fractions having same R_f values were mixed together and crystallised from methanol which gave all the colour tests for flavonoids⁴, $C_{26}H_{28}O_{15}$ m.p. 237–38° (Found : C, 53.40; H, 4.80. Calcd. for : C, 53.44; H, 4.82%), and M^+ 580 (EIMS at 70 eV); the acetyl derivative $C_{44}H_{46}O_{24}$ m.p. 212–13° (Found : C, 55.10; H, 4.78. Calcd. for : C, 55.11; H, 4.78%), M^+ 958 (EIMS at 70 eV), λ_{max} (MeOH) 335, 350; (NaOMe) 272, 377, 390; (NaOAc) 343, 384; (AlCl₃) 274, 330, 396 (sh); (AlCl₃/HCl) 267, 347, 352 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 340, 2 910, 1 672, 1 620, 1 280, 1 124 and 825 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr δ 2.34 (s, 3 C3-OAc), 2.40 (s, 3 C5-OAc), 6.40 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, C-6), 5.89 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-8), 7.34 (2H, d, J 2.6 Hz, C-2', C-6'), 7.20 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, C-3'), 2.38 (3H, s, C4'-OAc), 6.80 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, C-5'), 4.47 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, C-1'' anomeric proton of xylose), 2.05 (3H, s, C-2''-OAc), 2.14 (3H, s, C-3''-OAc), 4.40 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, C-1''' anomeric proton of glucose), 2.07 (3H, s, C-2'''-OAc), 2.10 (3H, s, C-3'''-OAc), 2.08 (3H, s, C-4'''-OAc), 2.09 (3H, s, C-6'''-OAc), 5.40–5.90 (6H, m, protons of glucose unit), m/z 417, 401, 286, 285, 257, 153, 152, 126, 124. On acid hydrolysis with 7% ethanolic H₂SO₄, it gave an aglycone, m.p.

280°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$, (M^+) 286. It was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystalline solid and identified as kaempferol by uv, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data. The hydrolysate was neutralised with BaCO₃ and tested for sugars by pc and tlc. Only D-glucose and D-xylose were identified on comparison with authentic samples. On permethylation⁵ followed by acid hydrolysis, it gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-xylose by (co-pc and co-tlc), suggesting that C4-OH group of the xylose was linked with C1-OH group of D-glucose. The enzymatic emulsin⁶ hydrolysis confirmed the presence of β -linkage between the sugars and the aglycone.

Thus the structure to the glycoside was assigned as kaempferol-7-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)-*O*- β -D-xylopyranoside (1).

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R = 7-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)-*O*- β -D-xylopyranoside

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